

Real Analysis of Phenomenological Velocity

by Parker Emmerson

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right.$$

$$\left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a > \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right)$$

Abstract : Performing this real analysis of the Phenomenological Velocity shows that the computed solution to the phenomenological velocity, $v = \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}$ from solving the equality:

$$h = \frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2 q s - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2}}{\alpha} = \frac{\sqrt{-(q-s-l\alpha)} \sqrt{(q-s+l\alpha)}}{\alpha} = \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}$$

within the Lorentz Coefficient satisfies the conditions placed upon it by a full Real Analysis of the form found when not using a specified constant for c . Therefore, the computed phenomenological velocity is a true solution.

$$\text{In[]:= Solve} \left[\frac{\sqrt{-(q-s-l\alpha)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(q-s+l\alpha)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha} = l \sin[\beta], \text{Reals} \right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ \beta \rightarrow -\text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{-c} \sqrt{\frac{q-s+l\alpha}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}} \sqrt{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2} (-q+s+l\alpha)}}{c l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \text{ if} \right. \right\},$$

$$\left(l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ s < q \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(s > q \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(s > q \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{-q+s}{l} \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ s < q \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{q-s}{l} \right)$$

$$\left. \left\{ \beta \rightarrow \pi + \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{-c} \sqrt{\frac{q-s+l\alpha}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}} \sqrt{\sqrt{c^2-v^2} (-q+s+l\alpha)}}{c l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \right. \right\},$$

if $\left(l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ s < q \right) \parallel$

$\left(s > q \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \parallel$

$\left(s > q \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{-q+s}{l} \right) \parallel$

$\left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ s < q \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{q-s}{l} \right)$

$$\left. \left\{ \beta \rightarrow \pi - \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\frac{q-s+l\alpha}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}} \sqrt{\sqrt{c^2-v^2} (-q+s+l\alpha)}}{\sqrt{c} l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \right. \right\},$$

if

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ s < q \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ s > q \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ s > q \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{-q+s}{l} \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ s < q \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{q-s}{l} \right)$

$$\left. \left\{ \beta \rightarrow \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\frac{q-s+l\alpha}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}} \sqrt{\sqrt{c^2-v^2} (-q+s+l\alpha)}}{\sqrt{c} l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \right. \right\},$$

if

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ s < q \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ s > q \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \geq \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ s > q \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{-q+s}{l} \right) \parallel$

$\left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ s < q \ \&\& \ \alpha \leq \frac{q-s}{l} \right)$

$$\left\{ l \rightarrow 0 \text{ if } \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right\},$$

$$s \rightarrow \left. \left\{ q \text{ if } \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \ || \ \left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left\{ s \rightarrow \left. \left\{ q \text{ if } \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\beta \rightarrow \left. \left\{ \pi - \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{l} \sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \alpha \sqrt{\frac{l \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}}}{\sqrt{c} l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left\{ \text{if } \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right.$$

$$\left\{ s \rightarrow \left. \left\{ q \text{ if } \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\beta \rightarrow \left. \left\{ \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{l} \sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \alpha \sqrt{\frac{l \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}}}{\sqrt{c} l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \text{ if } \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left\{ \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right.$$

$$\left\{ s \rightarrow \left. \left\{ q \text{ if } \left(l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\beta \rightarrow \left. \left\{ -\text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{\sqrt{-c} \sqrt{l} \sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \alpha \sqrt{\frac{l \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}}}{c l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left\{ \text{if } \left(l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \right) \ || \ \left(c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0 \right) \right.$$

$$\left\{ s \rightarrow \begin{array}{l} q \text{ if } (l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z}) \ || \\ (c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0) \end{array} \right\},$$

$$\beta \rightarrow \left. \begin{array}{l} \pi + \text{ArcSin}\left[\frac{\sqrt{-c} \sqrt{l} \sqrt{c^2 - v^2} \alpha \sqrt{\frac{l \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}}}{c l \alpha} \right] + 2 \pi c_1 \\ \text{if } (l > 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha > 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z}) \ || \\ (c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ c_1 \in \mathbb{Z} \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ \alpha < 0) \end{array} \right\}$$

In[]:= Reduce[

$$\left(\text{Sqrt}\left[\frac{a l + q - s}{\text{Sqrt}\left[1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right]} \text{Sqrt}\left[-\left(-(a l) + q - s \right) \text{Sqrt}\left[1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right] \right] \right) / a = l \text{Sin}[b], \{v\}, \text{Reals}]$$

Out[]:= $\left(q < s \ \&\&$

$$\left(\left(l < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(a < \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \left((c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \ || \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. (c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ || \ \left(a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\&$$

$$\left((c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \ || \ (c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(l > 0 \ \&\& \ \left(\left(a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& \ \left((c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \ || \ (c > 0 \ \&\&$$

$$-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \right) \right) \ || \ \left(a > \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\&$$

$$\left((c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \ || \ (c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\left(q = s \ \&\& \ \left(\left(l < 0 \ \&\& \ a < 0 \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\&$$

$$\left((c < 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \ || \ (c > 0 \ \&\& \ -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2}) \right) \right) \right) \ ||$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(l = 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(a < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \parallel \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left(a > 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \parallel \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(l > 0 \ \&\& a > 0 \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \parallel \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(q > s \ \&\& \left(\left(l < 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(a < \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \parallel \left(a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \parallel \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(l > 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \parallel \left(a > \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left(\left(c < 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \parallel \left(c > 0 \ \&\& -\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \parallel \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& c < 0 \right) \parallel \right. \\
 & \quad \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \quad \left. c > 0 \right) \parallel \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \right) \parallel \\
 & \quad \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \right) \parallel \\
 & \quad \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \right) \parallel \\
 & \quad \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < v < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q+s}{l} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \right) \parallel
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{In[*]:= Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(\text{l} \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta) \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(\text{l} \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta) / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}}{\alpha}, v]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Out[*]:= } & \left\{ \left\{ v \rightarrow \right. \right. \\ & - \left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right) / \\ & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}, \\ & \left\{ v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right) / \\ & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\} \} \\ v = & \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + \text{l}^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Modus ponens substitutions for the respective arc lengths and imaginary arc lengths.

$$v = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 w^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 s q + c^2 s^2 + c^2 w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. w^2 + q^2 - 2. s q + s^2 + w^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}$$

Rewrite variables $\alpha = a$, $b = \beta$

$$\text{In[*]:= } v := \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 \text{l}^2 a^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 s q + c^2 s^2 + c^2 \text{l}^2 a^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. \text{l}^2 a^2 + q^2 - 2. s q + s^2 + \text{l}^2 a^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Out[*]:= } & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 \text{l}^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ & \left. q < s \ \&\& \text{l} < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{-q + s}{\text{l}} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 \text{l}^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 \text{l}^2}} \ \&\& c < 0 \right) \ || \\ & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 \text{l}^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& \right. \\ & \left. \text{l} < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{-q + s}{\text{l}} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 \text{l}^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 \text{l}^2}} \ \&\& c > 0 \right) \ || \\ & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 \text{l}^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 \text{l}^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ & \left. q < s \ \&\& \text{l} < 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q + s}{\text{l}} \ \&\& \text{Sin}[b] = 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \right) \ || \end{aligned}$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q < s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q + s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q < s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q + s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q < s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a = \frac{-q + s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. l > 0 \ \&\& a > \frac{-q + s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& c < 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q < s \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. l > 0 \ \&\& a > \frac{-q + s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& c > 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q = s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a < 0 \ \&\& \sin[b] = 1 \ \&\& c < 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q = s \ \&\& l < 0 \ \&\& a < 0 \ \&\& \sin[b] = 1 \ \&\& c > 0 \right) ||$$

$$\left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q = s \ \&\& l = 0 \ \&\& \right.$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 & a < 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \quad || \quad \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q = s \ \&\& l = 0 \ \&\& a < 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q = s \ \&\& l = 0 \ \&\& a > 0 \ \&\& c < 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q = s \ \&\& l = 0 \ \&\& a > 0 \ \&\& c > 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q = s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a > 0 \ \&\& \sin[b] = 1 \ \&\& c < 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q = s \ \&\& l > 0 \ \&\& a > 0 \ \&\& \sin[b] = 1 \ \&\& c > 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q > s \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. l < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& c < 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& q > s \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. l < 0 \ \&\& a < \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& c > 0 \quad || \right. \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \right) || \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l < 0 \ \&\& \ a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right) || \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& \ c < 0 \right) || \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a = \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = 0 \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right) || \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \ q > s \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. l > 0 \ \&\& \ a > \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \ c < 0 \right) || \\
 & \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a > \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right) \\
 & \ln[] := \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \sin[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\
 & \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a > \frac{q-s}{l} \ \&\& \ \sin[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

ln[] := q := c

ln[] := s := 5

ln[] := a := π

In[]:= l := c

In[]:= b := 1.2468502254630345`

In[]:= c := 2.99792458`*^8

$$\text{In[]:= } \left(-\sqrt{c^2} < \frac{\sqrt{-a^2 c^2 l^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2 c^2 q s + c^2 s^2 + a^2 c^2 l^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}}{\sqrt{-1. a^2 l^2 + q^2 - 2. q s + s^2 + a^2 l^2 \text{Sin}[b]^2}} < \sqrt{c^2} \ \&\& \right. \\ \left. q > s \ \&\& \ l > 0 \ \&\& \ a > \frac{q - s}{l} \ \&\& \ \text{Sin}[b] = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 l^2 - q^2 + 2 q s - s^2}{a^2 l^2}} \ \&\& \ c > 0 \right)$$

Out[]:= True